

Deliverable D5.5

Simulation routine implementing environmental related findings

Deliverable report

Deliverable No.	D5.5	Work Package No.	WP5	Task/s No.	Tasks 5.4
Work Package Title	Development of integrated H&S and environmental systems				
Linked Task/s Title	Energy efficiency and environmental effects				
Status	Final	(Draft/Final Draf/Final)			
Dissemination level	PU	PU-Public			
Due date deliverable	2025-01-31	Submission date	2025-01-31		
Deliverable version	DEQ_D5.5_CHALMERS_20250131_vF				

Document Contributors

Deliverable responsible	CHALMERS	
Contributors	Organisation	
Gauti Asbjörnsson	CHALMERS	
Christina Lee	CHALMERS	
Adam Sköld	ROCTIM	
Reviewers	Organisation	
Harri Mikkola	SANDVIK	
Abdessadeq Zougari Ben Elkhayat	AKKODIS	
Violeta Vázquez	ZABALA	
Lorena Viladés	ANEFA	
Paulo Romero	ANEFA	

Document History

Version	Date	Comment
V1.0	2024/12/19	First Version
V2.0	2025/01/22	Final comments from final reviewers
V2.1	2025/01/31	Consolidated final version

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the authors' view. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the authors. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as consequence of project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allows a close follow up of main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them along the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, impact in the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

Taking social risks and quarry workers into account is especially crucial in WP5, as its specific goals include monitoring health and safety indicators in the production process, as well as and improving health and safety measures in plants.

Table of contents

Deliverable report.....	2
Document Contributors	2
Document History	2
Disclaimer	3
Table of contents	4
List of Abbreviations	6
1 Executive Summary.....	7
2 Introduction	8
2.1 Scope of the deliverable	8
2.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables.....	9
2.3 Social Risk.....	9
3 System & Framework Outlines.....	10
3.1 Plantsmith.....	10
3.2 IQS.....	11
3.3 Environmental assessment	12
4 Simulation routines.....	15
4.1 Data collection	16
4.1.1 Data Definitions	16
4.1.2 Automated Data Collection.....	18
4.1.3 Manual Data Collection.....	18
4.2 Evaluating Site Operations	20
4.2.1 Defining System Boundaries	20
4.2.2 Identifying Processing Activities.....	20
4.2.3 Activities after the Manufacturing Processes	20
4.3 Simulation Modelling	22
4.3.1 Process Configuration	22
4.3.2 Unit Configuration.....	23
4.3.1 Process and Environmental Simulation.....	24
4.4 Unit and Process Calibration	25
4.5 Input Production and Consumable Data	25
4.5.1 Product and Product Groups Configuration.....	25

4.6	Allocation	26
4.6.1	Allocation per Module	26
4.6.2	Allocation per Product/Product Group	27
4.7	Data Quality and Verification	27
4.7.1	Data Aggregation and Quality	27
4.7.2	EPD Verification	30
4.8	Simulation Results and Interpretation	31
4.8.1	Process Results.....	31
4.8.2	Environmental Panel.....	33
4.8.3	Contribution Analysis	35
4.8.4	Sensitivity Analysis	36
4.8.5	JSON.....	37
4.8.6	Accessibility and interpretability: Competence development.....	37
5	Environmental Impacts in Quarries.....	38
5.1	Overall Impacts Assessment	38
5.2	Standardization and certification	40
5.2.1	Sub-PCR for Unbound Aggregates	40
5.2.2	Digitalization for Environmental Assessment in the Industry	41
6	System integration (developers guide)	43
6.1	Data Management	43
6.2	Communication protocols.....	44
6.3	System trustworthiness	45
6.3.1	Documentation	46
7	Conclusions	48
8	References	49
9	List of Figures	50
10	List of Tables	51
	Annex I. Data Collection Guide	52
	Site-Specific Data Descriptions.....	52

List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
DCEP	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable
RM	Raw Materials
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
PCR	Product Category Rules
EPD	Environmental Product Declarations
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
CPR	Construction Product Regulation
BIM	Building Information Model

1 Executive Summary

DigiEcoQuarry is a Horizon 2020 project aiming to design, develop and validate in 5 pilot environments an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) comprising sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing. The aim is to provide integrated, digitalised, automatic and real-time process control for aggregates quarries.

The DigiEcoQuarry consortium combines the latest research and advanced technologies applied to quarry operations together with the integration of selected innovative digital solutions to boost the capacity of the aggregates sector, enhance health and safety conditions for workers, improve the selectivity and efficiency of the aggregates sites, maximise sustainability and resource efficiency in quarry operations and foster social acceptance of the extractive industry.

Within the DigiEcoQuarry project, Task 5.4 aims to further develop an online tool, known as *Plantsmith*, used for generating site specific Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) reports along with a summary report that can be the basis for an Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) for products produced on site. The LCA results are based on site-specific data connected to a simulation model built within the tool. EPDs are usually based on one year's worth of production data, however, this makes it difficult for quarry producers to identify and react to operating conditions that negatively impact the environmental performance of the products they produce.

Utilizing the digital platform of the IQS developed within DigiEcoQuarry, work has been done to investigate and demonstrate possibilities to retrieve product environmental data on a monthly basis, instead of yearly, for use in decision making at the plant, rather than EPD creation, using the *Plantsmith* expert system.

Deliverable 5.5: '*Report on Simulation routine implementing environmental related findings in quarrying*', aims to share insights from this work by providing documentation of the suggested working procedures for carrying out simulation based environmental impact assessment. It outlines procedures for both EPD creation and collecting more granular data for decision making in the plant using developments in the IQS connected to the *Plantsmith* expert system. Further, recommendations are given for future work on conducting environmental assessment in quarries leveraging digitalization.

2 Introduction

With the introduction of the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), all producers in Europe will need to start reporting on their environmental performance; aggregate producers are no exception. Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) are one way in which this data can be provided in a standardized format. However, the variability of production conditions linked to natural variations in source material, environmental factors due to the exposed nature of quarries to the elements, and varying customer demands, among others, make it difficult to use EPD data — usually representing one full year of production — for system improvements to reduce environmental impact. As reduction targets come closer, it will become more and more important for producers to actively reduce their environmental impact.

New technologies within Industry 4.0 like Internet of Things (IoT), big data, simulation, and cloud computing are suggested to bring increased productivity and efficiency for production chains (Nascimento et al., 2019), and many of these technologies are being implemented within the IQS in DigiEcoQuarry. These technologies are expected to contribute to improved environmental sustainability through functions like innovation, emission reduction, improved efficiency, and improved environmental awareness (Ghobakhloo, 2020).

Therefore, work has been carried out within Task 5.4 of WP5 in the project on how to implement environmental monitoring in conjunction with these technologies in the IQS to give aggregate users more granular environmental data for use in decision-making in the production system. The goal is to incite reductions in overall environmental impact.

The aim of this deliverable is to provide a holistic view on the routines and procedures needed to perform process and environmental impact evaluation with the platform *Plantsmith* and how this can be connected to the IQS for both data collection and providing relevant KPIs to dashboards for producers. Furthermore, it provides recommendations and insights for similar projects in the future and suggestions for relevant policy updates.

The environmental information and documentation created through the *Plantsmith* platform are based on the EPD framework while the process simulations are based on steady-state models. The EPD framework aims to provide quantitative environmental information for use in business-to-business communication on a product or service, and the process simulation enables automatic resource allocation. More information on EPDs can be found in Deliverable 5.4 of the project. The KPIs provided to producers through the IQS are, however, not within the EPD framework and should not be seen as equivalent to the environmental data provided in a verified EPD for public disclosure; rather, are aimed for confidential use by the producers themselves for improvement purposes.

The development of this deliverable is based on industrial applications of the platform and the feedback from the development of the state zero report in deliverable D5.4: *Report on Pre-verified Environmental Product Declaration documentation for pilot plants based on historical data*.

2.1 Scope of the deliverable

This report includes the holistic view on the routines and procedures in *Plantsmith* from a user perspective and the implementation of the platform in a 3rd party software such as the IQS from a developer's perspective. It also provides insights into the standardization processes for utilizing digitalization in environmental assessment at an industry level.

Section 3 provides a brief overview of the systems and frameworks utilized in Task 5.4., namely the *Plantsmith* platform, the IQS and the LCA approach for EPDs. Section 4 outlines the routines that users should follow to implement and fully utilize the capabilities of the tools described in section 3. Section 5 describes how these tools could be utilized for improving the environmental impact in quarries, and provides insights into what could be done at an industry level to realize such improvements, namely through standardization and data availability. Lastly section 6 provides routines from a developer perspective to enable data collection and KPI sharing through similar platforms as the IQS before a summary of the report in section 7.

2.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables

This document has been produced as part of the Horizon 2020 project DigiEcoQuarry and should be read in conjunction with the following documents (if possible, considering dissemination level) to provide relevant context to subsequent information:

1. DigiEcoQuarry Deliverable D1.4: Requirements for H&S improvement, environmental impact minimisation and energy and resources efficiency report. *Confidential*.
2. DigiEcoQuarry Deliverable D5.4: Report on Pre-verified Environmental Product Declaration documentation for pilot plants based on historical data.

2.3 Social Risk

DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have already been analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, and include potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allows a close follow up of main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them along the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, impact in the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction. For more information, please refer to the Deliverables 7.1 and 7.2.

Taking social risks and quarry workers into account is especially crucial in WP5, as its specific goals include monitoring safety and environmental indicators in the production process, as well as improving safety and environmental measures in plants. However, this deliverable is specifically focused on the environmental aspects of the project, and therefore, will not address safety-related issues within WP5.

3 System & Framework Outlines

Within WP5 (Development of integrated H&S and Environmental systems and Task 5.4 Environmental system evaluation and simulation), the deliverable D5.5 (Simulation routine implementing environmental finding in quarries) is a key component providing a summary of the development work from the user perspective, but also from a developer's perspective with information provided on how systems have been built and implemented.

The system can be defined either as the IQS connected to the environmental simulation platform Plantsmith, or as Plantsmith as a stand-alone application in the process, . Both approaches will be described in this report with respect to the user interaction and in developers' guidelines. Frameworks refer to existing guidelines and standards that have guided the development work for the systems itself.

3.1 Plantsmith

Plantsmith is a standalone cloud-based process simulation and environmental platform developed using cross-platform applications based on HTML, JavaScript and CSS for the front-end development and Python programming language for the back-end development and Rest-API for communication between modules. The Plantsmith platform consists of two main elements: the process simulation and the environmental calculations which together facilitate an industry specific process and environmental platform.

As a stand-alone application the user is able to create a production process model, enter the consumables used in the process manually and run simulations to calculate the environmental impact while producing drafts of relevant documents. Based on the user and company profile, a number of different functionalities can be either enabled or locked. These include certain process models, the environmental calculations, and financial calculations.

The modular approach has been used in the development of the platform. There is a defined communication format and protocol between different modules such as the simulation core, solver, model library, environmental database, report templates, and user interface. Internal functions can be called directly in the code, while communication with external modules is handled with Rest-APIs. The generated simulation results are stored centrally within a SQL server and the results are shown directly in the user interface. The results can also be summarised in Word reports or a JSON file that are downloaded to a local computer. The system structure for Plantsmith is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The system structure for Plantsmith

3.2 IQS

DigiEcoQuarry aims to develop an integrated platform, the Innovative Quarrying System (IQS), to enable complete digitalization for a quarry through ICT solutions, BIM, and AI technologies, aiming for full interoperability of the data sources across the different quarrying processes and through different expert systems for building and exploiting innovative and agile services. Plantsmith is one of the multiple client systems that are integrated into the solution. The software components developed to build the IQS for DigiEcoQuarry are illustrated in Figure 2 and are described in detail in D4.2: *Report on IQS design and architecture*.

Figure 2. System structure of the IQS.

3.3 Environmental assessment

Environmental assessment can be conducted using a multitude of frameworks and approaches. The approach taken in *Plantsmith* is an LCA approach based on the EPD framework. This has been chosen due to the quantitative nature of the assessment, as well as the standardized methodology used in the EPD framework that is valuable for producers in external communication, if the results are verified to produce an EPD. More information about the LCA approach and EPD framework can be found in D5.4 and in the licentiate thesis by Lee (2024).

To implement the LCA approach into *Plantsmith*, modular LCA has been used, as described by Brondi and Carpanzano (2011), for capturing the complexities of manufacturing systems. This is done by using modified Input-Process-Output units for ingoing and outgoing material and energy flows to each manufacturing unit. An overview of the modular LCA method can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The input-process-output modular LCA method suggested for different manufacturing activities in a production chain by Brondi & Carpanzano (2011).

The LCA modules represent the use of different auxiliary items or energy throughout the production process. The specific amounts of each auxiliary item or energy are calculated for each production process using the data collected by the sites or through the IQS. Therefore, Plantsmith can be seen to consist of the following components to allow for environmental assessment shown in Figure 4 in grey:

- Machinery models
- Simulation modules and algorithms
- LCA modules
- Report templates

To conduct the environmental assessment for a plant so that it matches the realities of that specific plant, however, the tool needs user input. The specific actions required of the user to conduct the environmental assessment are highlighted in Figure 4 in blue and green, and are what will be further described in section 4 of this document.

Figure 4: An overview of the workflow highlighting user actions and components of the Plantsmith tool needed for conducting environmental assessment using the tool (Lee et al., 2024).

4 Simulation routines

To develop an environmental profile of a quarry or mine, several interlinked steps need to be conducted, as highlighted in Figure 5. Specifically, these actions can be described by eight iterative steps, summarised as:

- **Collection of yearly data on consumables and production specifications.** High quality data can be collected from invoices, internal monitoring records, sensors, and sales data, among other sources. Examples of lower quality data include estimations based on site conditions or data collected from other sites with similar conditions.
- **Evaluation of site activities from a life cycle perspective.** Information is collected on the different activities related to the product, from its extraction until where the product leaves the factory gate. Activities after the product has left the control of the pilot site, e.g., transport to customers is not mandatory to consider in the historical data documentation.
- **Modelling of production processes.** The information collected is used to model the production process in the platform. This ranges from the extraction to a final product that can be transported out of the site. The modelling of the site depends on the system definitions of the quarry, the process layout and installed equipment.
- **Configuration and calibration of the process models.** Based on the site data the process modelled needs to be configured and calibrated to generate representative performance of the quarry over a defined period.
- **Allocation of environmental burdens to products.** Combining the data gathered in the initial stages with the process model produced, the environmental burdens are allocated to the different products produced.
- **Assessment of data quality.** All the data used for generating the models and allocating the environmental burdens should be checked its quality by checking the source of the data, the plausibility of the results by benchmarking and assessing to see if any data gaps remain.
- **Sensitivity of the results.** The sensitivity of the results needs to be evaluated by varying the consumables within a defined range to quantify the sensitivity of the results to particular consumable inputs and how the results would change if consumption varied in the future.
- **Generate documentation.** Background LCA and EPD reports are autogenerated in Plantsmith and shared with the pilot sites to for interpretation of the quantitative results to complete the final stage of the LCA methodology according to ISO 14040.

As stated, the process is iterative and not necessarily sequential, where multiple steps can, and should, be done in parallel often returning to previous steps as new information and knowledge is gained through collecting the data, setting up the platform and interpreting the results. New iterations are often caused by identifying gaps and missing data along the way. An overview of the process can be seen in Figure 5.

What each of these steps can entail for producers is described in detail in this section and can be seen as guidelines for producers to help them fully exploit the *Plantsmith* tool.

Figure 5: Illustration of the process followed during the assessment.

4.1 Data collection

This section outlines the many data points needed to build the process models and run environmental assessment based on the real running conditions of a plant. As previously stated, the routines are not necessarily sequential, and is highly recommended to conduct data collection in parallel with steps 2 and 3 connected to the site operations and process simulations, returning to the data collection step as more knowledge is gained.

4.1.1 Data Definitions

There are many different data points that are needed to successfully conduct the process simulations and environmental calculations. When discussing data in LCA, it is often split into background data and foreground data. Background data can be thought of as data that is controlled by other systems and where you have no influence, for example, data on how grid electricity is produced and transported to your site, and its associated inputs and outputs to the environment (an aggregate producer cannot control how the electricity producer runs their systems to produce the electricity, and likely have no direct influence on how they produce electricity). Plantsmith contains this background data within the LCA modules built into the platform (more information about these can be found in section 3.3), however, the user also has the option to input their own background data if they have, for example, a specific EPD related to that data point.

Even if the electricity production itself is out of the control of the aggregate producer, how much electricity is used and which supplier is chosen is within the aggregate producer's control and so can be thought of as foreground data. Figure 6 shows an overview of common background and foreground data referred to in the environmental assessment using *Plantsmith*. As the background data is already contained within the Plantsmith platform, data collection refers to the foreground data only.

Figure 6: An overview of common background and foreground data in an LCA study for construction products.

Foreground data can be split into three main categories: consumables data, technical data, and production data.

- **Consumables data** refers to the amount of all the inputs and outputs from the system. This can include any energy needed in the production system, materials used for maintenance and upkeep of machines in the system, or external materials that go into the product during the production process. It also includes any wastes or emissions produced from the system, for example packaging waste, air emissions, or scrap parts. For aggregate systems this could be diesel or grid electricity for energy, oils and metal parts for machinery, salt that is added to any products, and municipal or hazardous wastes collected from the production site.
- **Technical data** refers to data on the processes used in the production system, for example the running conditions and activities that occur throughout the production system. This helps plan what consumable data you will need to collect.
- **Production data** refers to amount of each product or production waste that is produced by the system, as well as information about the products and wastes e.g. content of the products or production waste, or the quality/classifications of the products.

The above definitions help to understand what data needs to be collected, but does not indicate how the data can be collected. There are two main methods for collecting the foreground data: real data or modelling.

- **Real data** can be collected from direct measuring e.g. from sensors like water counters, diesel pumps or weighing systems; sales data on production; bills from suppliers; or expert estimations.
- **Modelling data** can be calculated using literature models or software, and can be used for e.g. estimating direct emissions or energy consumption.

How the data is collected can impact the quality of the results: the different ways the data, and the processing of said data, can impact the quality of the results is addressed in section 4.7.

With multiple data points to collect and many possible sources, using solely manual data collection is timely and involves coordination between many people involved in the operations. One of the key advantages with the IQS is to automatically collect parts of this data. Further, for EPD creation, one year’s worth of data is needed which does not provide a high-level of granularity for detecting possible improvements in environmental performance from changes to the operating conditions. Automating some data collection can increase the frequency of data collection without the need for extra time resources. Technical data usually comes from the experts involved in the manufacturing process and can often be qualitative based on their detailed knowledge of the system, which makes it difficult to automate. However, the production and consumables data requires more quantitative data and can be automated. The automated data collection process implemented in the IQS is discussed further in section 4.1.2 while guidelines on manual data collection are addressed in section 4.1.3.

4.1.2 Automated Data Collection

Manual data collection is highly time consuming, and often the data required is already being collected by other systems in the quarry for other purposes.

To send production and consumables data automatically, a dedicated proxy was established by AKKODIS. By using this, the consumables were imported to the DataLake, from which the relevant expert systems can access the data, including Plantsmith. Plantsmith can fetch this data once a month and automatically re-run the environmental calculations with the new data to provide estimates of environmental performance on a more frequent basis. More information about the protocol can be found in D4.2.

4.1.3 Manual Data Collection

This section gives an overview of key production and consumable data points that are needed for the environmental assessment in a standard quarry, starting with the production data. The production data presented in Table 1 and Table 2 is collected from the site for a given reference period e.g. one year, known as the reference year.

Table 1: Production data from an annual production.

Data Required	Unit	Comments
Total production.	tonne/year	The total stock produced during the reference year.
Production hours	hours	The total number of hours within the reference year

Table 2: Product level data

Product	Unit
--/-- mm	tonne/year

As previously described, the consumables data consists of auxiliary and waste materials used or produced on site. This data can be collected through bills, measurements, lab reports, and communication with the site. Table 3 and Table 4 **Error! Reference source not found.** illustrate the identified standard consumables and waste data needed from the site for the reference year. More details on the data needed can be found in Annex I.

Table 3: Consumable data from the reference year

Data	Unit	Comments
Diesel	l/year	Diesel used in drill rigs, excavators, wheel loaders, and trucks
Electricity	kwh/year	Electricity used during processing operations and for office buildings
Water	m3/year	Water used for site preparation, dust prevention, and office use
Explosives	kg/year	Explosives used for blasting
Lubricants	l/year	Lubricants used in yellow machines
Metals	kg/year	Metals due to replacing crusher liners and spare parts for yellow machines
Rubber	kg/year	Rubber to replacing tyres of yellow machines and conveyor belts
AdBlue	l/year	AdBlue used in yellow machines
Plastics	kg/year	Plastics from the use of plastic packaging
Wood	kg/year	Wooden pallets used for transportation
Flocculants	kg/year	Flocculants used for dust prevention

Table 4: Waste data

Type	Unit	Comments
Mixed Waste	kg/year	Includes any non-hazardous waste such as metals, wood, rubber, and municipal solid waste.
Hazardous waste	kg/year	Includes any hazardous waste such as contaminated clothing, batteries, and electronics.
Inert Waste Rock	tonne/year	The difference between the combined total quantity of blasted material and overburdened material to the total quantity of products produced.

4.2 Evaluating Site Operations

Key for understanding the technical data needed to be collected, as well as for being able to produce a model of the production facility for conducting simulations, is an in depth understanding of the aggregate plant itself. For many operators, this is an inherent part of their role and does not require much. However, it is also important to be able to describe the operations to match the LCA framing of the production facility, known is the system boundaries. This is described further below.

4.2.1 Defining System Boundaries

Production facilities rely on many other processes within a value chain, and exactly which activities are under the producer's influence, or which contribute to their environmental impact, is not always clear-cut. Hence, in LCA, particular guidelines and descriptions need to be provided to clearly define what is the production system being described. A starting point for this process is identifying the type of aggregate being evaluated. These include natural aggregates, recycled aggregates, and manufactured aggregates. Currently all aggregate types mentioned fall under the category of 'construction product' where definitions and methods are determined by the EU standard EN15804. However, a c-PCR is under development for unbound aggregates that give a clearer framework of how to handle different types of aggregates. Further information on this is given in section 5.2.1. For DigiEcoQuarry the focus has been on the natural aggregates, which are extracted from quarries, pits, river sub-surfaces or from the sea sub-surface. Activities may include crushing for size reduction, water treatments and screening to achieve a desired size gradation. Therefore, the system boundaries considered are in relation to natural aggregates only in *Plantsmith*.

Further to the type of aggregate in question, the type of facility should also be defined. In *Plantsmith*, the user can choose from three pre-programmed options of a crushed, dredging, or natural gravel facility for defining the facility type.

4.2.2 Identifying Processing Activities

Once the aggregate and facility type are identified, all the processing activities or 'manufacturing processes' need to be identified and allocated to a module to help with allocating environmental burdens later in the environmental calculations. The modules to which activities are allocated are determined by the EPD framework, namely EN 15804, and can be seen in Figure 7. Activities can include, for example, blasting, crushing, screening, washing, or dredging.

4.2.3 Activities after the Manufacturing Processes

The lifecycle of a product does not end after the manufacturing process is complete, and many impacts can occur in activities after this stage. Within the EPD framework, it is compulsory to also report impacts that occur during the disposal or 'end-of-life' of a product, as well as any impacts that go beyond the product system itself. More information on what these stages cover can be found in the EN 15804 standard and in D5.4.

4.2.3.1 External transport (A4 module)

The external transport of the products is an optional part of the EPD documentation. The variation will be significant in many cases, making it difficult to get an average estimate. However, in the c-PCR for Aggregates from EPD Norge, the following guidelines are provided:

- 50 Km should be used as the default travelling distance for aggregates from the manufacturing or intermediate storage site

- Case-specific EPDs shall use actual freight distances within a given project

An example of a case-specific scenario was developed in DEQ. Based on automatic data logging on one of the trucks used for transporting the material from quarry to construction location, the following scenario was defined:

- 95% of trips were to the same location. Trips could vary with up to 12km on a return trip (alternative routes used) with an average return trip of 98 km. The utilization was assumed to be 48% (96% on the way to the location and 0% coming back). Average speed had a range from 31-48km/h.

Figure 7: Different modules to which activities in the manufacturing process should be allocated for the production site in question. As can be seen, these activities are part of the whole lifecycle of the product.

4.2.3.2 End-of-Life (C module)

It is often not known exactly how a product will be processed during its disposal at the manufacturing stage, especially for products like aggregates that can be used over 50+ years in their final applications. Therefore, it is common practice to use a generic scenario that can be assumed to be representative for the product.

Plantsmith has an in-built scenario so that the environmental impact for end-of-life can be automatically calculated and included in the different product's environmental profile. It is described as:

- Unbound aggregate remains in its original use yet is moved to a new location. The new location is estimated to be 20 km from its original position and transported using a EURO 3 34-40 Tonnes Lorry with an 61% Load Factor.

As the impact is automatically calculated, the user is not required to provide alternative scenarios, or data concerning the end-of-life of the products. However, if the user has calculated the environmental impact of a more product specific scenario using the same LCIA characterization models as stated in the PCR standard, the values for C-Module can be manually overridden in the templates. If this is done, it must be clearly stated in the background report.

4.2.3.3 Benefits & loads beyond the system boundary (D Module)

Similarly to module C, module D is often not known for specific aggregate products, and, therefore, a scenario is used. Plantsmith automatically calculates the environmental impact for module D using the scenario

described in module C and assuming 10% of the aggregate product is lost during its lifetime and will need to be replaced. Therefore, the user is not required to provide further information concerning this stage in the product lifecycle. For more information on how module D is calculated, see section 4.4.1 in the licentiate thesis by Lee (2024).

4.3 Simulation Modelling

With an in depth understanding of the activities involved in the manufacturing process, a model can be built in Plantsmith using the various machinery models connected together to form a complete model of the plant. The process layout, equipment selection, condition of the units and their operational strategy all determine the production performance over time, and therefore, time should be taken to match and calibrate the model as closely as possible to the running conditions of the plant. Plantsmith provides a steady-state simulation of the production to provide the user with an approximated performance based on the user mass-balancing of the circuit to match the general performance of the production over a given period. In cases where multiple operational scenarios are being evaluated, additional factors must be considered. See section 4.8.4 for more details.

4.3.1 Process Configuration

The definition of system boundaries and the mode of extraction defines the mode of operation and the selection of templates in the platform. By defining if the process handles natural aggregates, extracted by blasting, dredging or excavation the user can start creating the flowsheet of the process and its operations.

The platform comes with equipment library categorised based on the operational categorisation. These can be drilling and blasting, crushers, screens, mills, classifiers, water treatments, conveyors, bins, stockpiles, mobile machinery and more. The library is continuously being expanded with different types of models and equipment the platform develops, accommodating both academic and industrial use cases. The user starts with a blank canvas as illustrated in Figure 8, selects the model library and starts dragging in relevant equipment and model based on the purpose of the simulation and the model preferences, more details on how to calibrate each model can be found in section 4.4. Each icon represents a unit in the process and for a good representation of the process, all units should be included as they contribute to the overall energy use. When the units have been placed on the canvas, the models are connected together to form a coherent flowsheet. Adjustments on location of units and stream connection should be done to improve the readability of the process flowsheet, see Figure 9.

Figure 8. Empty canvas ready for flowsheet creation.

Figure 9. A simple flowsheet of an aggregate process.

In some cases, quarries might have completely different operational strategies over the reference period as the market demand changes. With significant alteration in the flowsheet or product groups, a separated flowsheet is recommended: either as a completely different flowsheet model or as a different version of the same process within the version control in Plantsmith (located on the right-hand side of the banner).

4.3.2 Unit Configuration

Each unit consists of a number of inputs and outputs. The primary input and output are the stream that connects each unit with any other unit as described in 4.1.2. Multiple streams can be connected to the same input and the calculations will sum up the properties as a function of mass flow. However, if two or more streams are pulled from the same output then the streams have the same properties, and a copy is made effecting the mass balance. This is to enable running multiple scenarios with the same flowsheet to compare process performance in the same flowsheet. Some unit models like screen will inherently have multiple outputs as is the case for the actual units. Most of the values for the streams can be defined in different source

blocks. These can be defined from either a stockpile source unit, or a drilling and blasting source unit and includes mass flow, material density, Bond work index, abrasion index and other material properties that define the source material. Other stream properties are accumulative and do change depending on the unit models defined in the process and their operation. These include specific energy, specific fuel consumption and specific cost: all defined with the functional unit of per tonne material processed. Figure 10 illustrates the configuration of the stream properties in one of the source blocks.

Figure 10. A configuration of the stream properties in the source block.

Each unit model includes a set of design, operational and mathematical variables which defines the operational performance of that particular unit together with the stream properties. Most models have a unique set of variables. However, some might have a very similar set. For example, all cone crushers will have a representation of the smallest operational gap between the mantle and the concave, referred to as close-side settings or CSS, or a screen model might have aperture of the screen as a design variable. The set of available variables depends on the intended use of the models and the user's preference. Some models are preconfigured to enable a quick configuration of the units and plant, and will have a performance that is nominal for that unit based on data from site surveys or manufacturers. Other units include more mathematical variables and enable the user to calibrate their unit and process for a more accurate representation of the process model with the actual process, described in 4.1.4 to capture an appropriate breakage behaviour or separation cut point in screens.

4.3.1 Process and Environmental Simulation

When the process has been configured and calibrated, the process simulation can be executed. The simulation core is based on the principle of steady-state, which covers mass balance, energy balance and cost balance to generate stream variable values for specific energy, specific fuel consumption and specific cost.

Through the EPD and LCA Menu, the user enters site-specific information on the yearly production and the different resources consumed. With the EPD calculation, an automatic allocation is created and environmental impacts are calculated. For more information see section 4.8.

4.4 Unit and Process Calibration

Units and process calibration can be done on different abstraction levels. No automated calibration routines are included in the platform and all comparisons need to be done on a separate platform such as MATLAB or Excel.

Within the EPD framework, the data is collected for a year of operation. However, the process will experience several disturbances, as a fact of normal operations, over a year that is not included nor reflected in the process models as they are steady-state models. These disturbances can be from aspects of wear, maintenance, failures and variability in the source properties and are not included in the simulations, making it difficult to fully compare the simulation to the actual reality. However, if the same operational strategy has been applied throughout the year, the ratios between the different products can be used as a proxy for the calibration by adjusting the unit configuration to achieve an appropriate mass and energy balance throughout the process as this will improve the representability of the automatic allocation described in 4.2.3. For higher level calibration, which might be needed to evaluate process improvements regarding process yields or resource efficiency, a shorter period should be used where the process is operating close to the intended design capacity and unit models which includes mathematical variables should also be applied.

To evaluate the implementation of the model, a comparison between an average mass flow over 10 minutes, given that the process is stable within that time frame, and the simulated mass could be used, where the accuracy of the process model is quantified as a difference in the form of an error between the actual process and the simulation. There are different ways of quantifying the error, the most common way is to quantify the error with root mean square (RMSE). The same procedure could be applied to a calibration with regard to particle size distribution.

4.5 Input Production and Consumable Data

Considering the steady-state nature of the simulations, it is difficult to capture fluctuations and changes that happen in reality, especially when considering a one-year time frame. Therefore, it is important to input real data on production and consumption to gain useful and reliable results. For manual input data, production and consumption data can be entered directly in the EPD tab identified by a leaf symbol in both the 'Production' and 'Consumables' sections. To gain more insights into the production, it is also important to include the individual products and group them appropriately to estimate their individual environmental performance. This can be done by creating 'Product Groups' under the production section in Plantsmith. More details on how product groups can be created are provided in section 4.5.1. It is not necessary to create product groups either, or each product group can consist of just one product, giving the user a large amount of flexibility in how the results of the environmental assessment are presented.

After the product groups have been created and connected to the model, it is possible to automate the data collection through the DataLake, as long as the naming of each product is consistent between platforms, and reference period for the data is specified (e.g. production per month or year).

4.5.1 Product and Product Groups Configuration

The internal allocation between different aggregate products is done by creating sub-classes of products referred to as product groups. Products within the same product group are assumed to consume the same amount of resources for their production due to their similar processing needs. Production data within the boundaries of the product system are allocated to each group on the basis of the total mass produced in one year within that group, if not specified otherwise. Specific processing steps that are only applied to a single

product group, or limited to selected product groups, should only be allocated to respective product groups. This applies to the use of any specific additives as well.

The majority of EPDs have product groups that are linked to the extraction of products from each individual crushing stage. If the crushing plant has 3 stages of crushing, there are often 4 defined product groups: Blasted product, screened and crushed with a primary crushing stage, screened and crushed with a secondary crushing stage, and screened and crushed with a tertiary crushing stage. According to EN 15804, material flows carrying specific inherent properties shall always be allocated reflecting the physical flows, irrespective of the allocation chosen for the process. For the production of aggregates, this is reflected by the change in specific energy (kWh/t) for each product group, which is distinct with only minor changes between products within the same product group. Table 2 shows an example of how some products may be grouped and the production data collected for input.

The sum of the allocated inputs and outputs of a unit process shall always be equal to the inputs and outputs of the unit process before allocation. This means no double counting or omission of inputs or outputs through allocation should occur.

Table 5: Product level data

Product Groups:	Product	Unit
Group 1	--/-- mm	tonne/year
Group 2	--/-- mm	tonne/year
	--/-- mm	tonne/year
Etc.	--/-- mm	tonne/year

4.6 Allocation

Once the models are built based on the technical data collected and the production and consumption data inputted into Plantsmith, the resources needed for each product in production can be allocated to gain an individual environmental profile for each product/ product group defined. To understand where environmental burdens occur in the manufacturing process, allocation occurs in two steps: first per module, and second per product/product group.

4.6.1 Allocation per Module

First is the allocation to different modules in the system, A1 – A3. This refers to resource use that is used with specific operations in the process. The general rule is that the allocation is done based on mass. However, as stated in section 4.1.6, specific processing steps that are only applied to a single product group, or limited to selected product groups, should only be allocated to respective product groups. This same principle concerns different steps in the systems. For example, blasting is only applied to A1, and water might only be applied to the production of aggregates in A3. This configuration is site-dependent. However, it needs to reflect the physical reality of the production of aggregates within that system. Each product shares an equal allocation

within A1 and A2 based on mass. The sum of the allocated inputs and outputs of consumables should be equal to 100% between A1, A2 and A3.

Table 5 demonstrates the allocation of diesel into the A1, A2, and A3 life cycle modules, based on the operations involving the use of yellow machines. Driller SANDVIK DX800 is used for drilling holes which is part of the raw material extraction process, hence it is included in the A1 life cycle module. Whereas CAT 390 is used for loading the rocks onto the truck, which is part of the loading and hauling process, hence it is included in A2. Similar allocation has been performed for other yellow machinery based on their use. Another example is water consumption where 90% is allocated to A1 since the majority of it is being used for site preparation and dust prevention and a small portion is being used in offices (See Table 6).

Table 6: Description of the use of yellow machines

Yellow machines	Use	Quantity in litres per year	Life cycle module
Machine 1	Drilling	--	A1
Machine 2	Clearing, picking of large rocks., and loading.	--	A1
Machine 2	--	--	A2
Etc.	--	--	A3

4.6.2 Allocation per Product/Product Group

It is not until the second allocation phase of the allocation within A3 where a distinction between the different product groups is created. Here the resources allocated to A3 are distributed based on both mass and specific energy. Electrical power or diesel used in the production are distributed based on calculated specific energy of producing each production stream while other resources are distributed based on mass of the product produced.

4.7 Data Quality and Verification

To assess the reliability, accuracy, and precision of the results gained through the environmental assessment, the data quality needs to be assessed, and a verification process is suggested. These are described in the following section.

4.7.1 Data Aggregation and Quality

After the appropriate data has been collected, it often needs to be processed to make it suitable and useful for inputting into the environmental assessment. This is known as data aggregation and can impact the quality of the results, on top of the data itself.

For EPD creation, the data needs to be aggregated so that it represents one full year. This can involve adding up monthly bills, compiling different sensor readings, extrapolating modelling data to cover the whole year, or estimating average running conditions for different processes that may fluctuate over the year. This in itself

can impact the quality of the data as the same product may have a different environmental impact throughout the year due to differences in the production process, and is partly why higher granularity is being sought in the DEQ project through the IQS. However, as the EPD aims at providing an overview of the environmental performance of a product, an average scenario is more relevant for customers who can then use EPDs in their own decision making.

Further, the data needs to be aggregated for each activity to allow for allocation. Even though the overall impact should be the same (aggregation should not lead to any flows being missing or added in), it affects where the impact is shown and which products receive the burdens. If the data quality is low when aggregating the data per activity, it can make it much harder to identify where improvements can be made.

Data quality is a vital part of EPD creation and LCA in general. It can also cover many different aspects considering the large amount, and variation in the types, of data needed discussed earlier. However, three areas for data quality are named for consideration in the PCR will be described first before considering quality aspects for individual data points.

In EN 15804, data quality is often discussed by its representativeness. This is split into three different areas to consider how well the data represents the system of study. Although this can be more relevant for background data, it is still relevant for the foreground data particularly when data gaps have been identified and filled in, for example if water data for the year of the study was missing so data from the year before, or data from a similar production site within your company has been used instead. The three areas to examine the representativeness of the data are described below:

- **Time:** also referred to as the ‘temporal representativeness’. This is where the data you have used is assessed against the year the EPD is stated to represent. Data is assessed to have a very good temporal representativeness when it matches the year of study (reference year). Background data from generic datasets usually take a long time to compile so rarely come from the same year of the EPD study. However, for background data, it is the validity year that should be in the same range as the reference year, rather than the reference year of the background data. On the other end of the scale, data that is 6-10 years old is seen as poor quality.
- **Location:** also referred to as ‘geographical representativeness’. In this category, how well the location for the data collected matches the defined site in the EPD is assessed. For foreground data, data collected from the site itself is seen to be of very good quality. However, this is extremely unlikely if generic data sets have been used for the background data. Most generic datasets discuss location in terms of a region or country, and if this matches with the site location for your EPD then a good data quality is still achieved.
- **System:** also referred to as ‘technical representativeness’. This area focuses on the processes and materials used in the system of study, and how well they match the reality of the site given in the EPD. If all the significant processes are captured and materials match with the reality, a very good data quality is achieved. However, if data for adjacent or similar materials or processes have been used e.g. information on processes used for marine dredged aggregates rather than crushed aggregates, then it is assessed to be very poor quality.

When it comes to foreground data and individual data points, there can be other aspects to consider on top of the representativeness. This can include:

- **Accuracy:** there is often a common belief that using real data is always more accurate than using modelling data, however this is not always true. For example, collecting real data on emissions from an open site is difficult and will almost always lead to an underestimation of the emissions, as not all are captured. In this instance, modelling the emission data can be much more accurate considering the knowledge that exists on the chemical and physical properties of emission releasing activities like combustion. However, in other instances, real data can be much more reliable than modelling data, for example for estimating the total energy used considering variations in a production process. Furthermore, real data collected with sensors that are poorly calibrated or can drift under use can also lead to lower accuracy. Therefore, it is important that the data source is individually examined and assessed so that the accuracy is adequate to get reliable results in the environmental assessment.
- **Data source:** Similar to thinking about the accuracy of the data used, it is also important to consider the source of the data, and whether that could negatively impact the results from the environmental assessment. For example, if estimates have been used, the quality of the data used can vary greatly depending on how competent the person estimating is in that area. Similarly, if data has been collected from sub-contractors, there can be questions on how reliable their data collection methods are. Even models can vary from good quality models to poor quality models, so the individual models behind modelling data can also impact the quality of the final results. If data has to be used from an unreliable source due to important gaps, this should be clearly described in the background documentation of the environmental assessment.
- **Aggregation:** as already discussed, the process of aggregation can impact the results of the environmental assessment. This is because data might be collected continuously or in discreet intervals and so any fluctuations in performance are removed by the aggregation process. This does make it easier for communicating the results in the EPD, however, it also makes it more difficult to identify improvement areas based on optimizing running conditions, and not every unit of product may carry the same environmental burden.

4.7.1.1 Data Transparency

Data quality can be subjective and is a complicated topic. Therefore, the final step to ensure that data quality is adequate is providing clear and detailed information on factors that impact the data quality. Part of the EPD creation is providing documentation on the important decisions made and data collected that could have influenced the quality of the final results. Most of this is done in the 'Background LCA report' which is only shared with the verifier. This is partly because it can be a lot of information that is overwhelming to include in an EPD, but also to help ensure that no data that could be harmful for the company is shared publicly. However, some of the information on the data quality should be shared within the EPD itself, for example, information of the generic data used or missing data. For exactly what should be reported in the EPD itself, it is good to consult both the PCR and GPI. To learn more about how to keep good documentation, we

recommend looking into good data management techniques, for example Data Management Best Practices from UC San Diego¹.

Digitalization can help producers in easing the documentation burden significantly. One way is through using customized templates for the reporting itself, as implemented already in Plantsmith, minimizing the amount of work that needs to be done by the producers. Another way is through utilizing metadata related to the quality of datasets so that this information can be automatically shared. This topic is discussed further in section 5.2.2.

4.7.2 EPD Verification

Verification plays a crucial role in the EPD framework by building trust in the information presented, while also maintaining confidentiality by not disclosing all raw data that could reveal sensitive details about a manufacturing process: information competitors might find valuable. Verification involves assessing the plausibility of the data used and published, but it cannot guarantee that all information is completely accurate or correct. Therefore, it's important to report any errors that you notice in an EPD as soon as possible so that corrections can be made promptly. Mistakes can happen, and there is usually no penalty for submitting an update if an error is found in an EPD for your own product, so it is in your best interest to do so.

The verification process can typically follow three different pathways, depending on the program operator and the resources available. More information on the verification pathways specific to your chosen program operator can be found in the GPI. The pathways include:

- Third-party verification
- Internal verification
- Tool verification complimented with one of the above.

Third party verification is conducted by a qualified external expert who have met certain conditions. Your programme operator may list approved third-party verifiers for their programme who can conduct this work.

Internal verification can be conducted in different ways. A more robust method is through verifying a process for producing EPDs within your company through a third-party verifier. This means that any EPDs produced through this method can be checked by a competent person within the company before being published. Some programme operators may allow for someone within the company who has relevant competence and has not been involved in the work for producing the EPD to verify its content. Consult your specific programme operator to understand what type of verification is allowed.

Lastly, a specially developed tool or software that has been verified for producing EPDs for certain products can be used. If such a tool is used for calculating the LCA results presented in the EPD, third party or internal verification can be done a lot quicker as less data points need to be checked.

EPD International gives instructions for pre-verified LCA tools in Annex C of their General Programme Instructions. Although using a pre-verified tool simplifies the verification process, verification is still needed to ensure the data uploaded into the tool is correct. Using pre-verified tools though can save time and money in the verification process for the EPD owner as parts of the verification process, namely linked to the data used

¹ <https://library.ucsd.edu/research-and-collections/research-data/plan-and-manage/data-management-best-practices.html>

in the background LCA study, will have already been fulfilled. According to EPD International, a pre-verified tool should contain:

- Suitable datasets to cover the background LCA study of the product
- Calculations models that produce correct data for the product

During the verification process of the tool, the following aspects can be checked:

- | | |
|---|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Choice of data & datasets ▪ Data quality, sources, and references ▪ Data security | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Compliance with relevant PCR ▪ Compliance with the General Programme Instructions ▪ Description of indicators and the methods behind them |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ LCA modelling hypotheses including system boundary, cut-offs, allocation rules, and calculation rules ▪ Functionality to produce relevant reports including a tool project report, LCA report and LCA results/EPD report | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Procedures established for updating the information within the tool along with logs of updates ▪ Software usability and security so that pre-verified data cannot be manipulated |

Future work with Plantsmith includes starting the tool verification process to make EPD verification easier for producers.

4.8 Simulation Results and Interpretation

The simulations are steady-state which covers mass balance, energy balance and cost balance. When the process has been linked to defined product groups, the environmental impact per group can be calculated. If the simulation has reached mass balance, the simulation log will state:

Figure 11. Simulation log for a successfully completed simulation.

There are 4 levels of information that can be provided to the user as a part of the simulation routine. The initial one is the message illustrated in Figure 11. The remaining three notifications can be troubleshooted using Plantsmith help pages and include:

- Note: Information provided from the equipment model
- Warning: warning defined in the code by the developer, such as model outside the specific variable range
- Error: failed simulation, mass balance not achieved.

4.8.1 Process Results

Provided that the process model has reached a mass and energy balance, there are different process responses that are illustrated in the user interface. Some are illustrated directly in the canvas, either next to

the equipment model or in the stream. The results panel that appears after the simulation can also be accessed by the button shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Results button within the Plantsmith interface.

Results can also be extracted in different formats. Beside the JSON file that is described in section 4.8.5, the simulation results can be extracted in different formats by the buttons shown in Figure 13. There the simulation results can be extracted as a PDF file, CSV or XLS.

Figure 13. Report generation buttons within the Plantsmith interface.

In the results panel to the left in the user interface, the following information is illustrated:

- Particle size distribution for all streams
- Specific energy for all streams
- Equipment utilization
- Conversion of all stream properties.

Figures 14 and 15 illustrate an example of the particle size distribution that can be plotted and the specific energy as the material gets processed, respectively. Different colour schemes are used for each stream to simplify the identification of different streams.

Figure 14. Particle size distribution for all the streams.

Figure 15. Specific energy for all the streams.

In the canvas itself, different results can be shown that are based on the unit model and the stream. Figure 16 illustrates an example of stream and unit model results. The unit model results are model-dependent and will differ depending on the model applied in the backend.

Figure 16. Example of results for the stream and unit model.

4.8.2 Environmental Panel

The environmental module of the platform can be accessed by processing the EPD button in the taskbar, depicted by a leaf. Once clicked, the EPD and LCA Menu appears to the left of the canvas, see Figure 17. The corresponding tabs are used to enter all the relevant information collected by the user for the production site needed to quantify the environmental impact. This can include production data, consumables, site-specific information and more.

Figure 17: EPD and LCA Menu in the platform.

After the process simulation and allocation of resources to different product groups, each impact category can be quantified. In the results tab, the impact for each stage (A1-A3) is shown, and the impacts for each product group: see Figure 18 for an example of the core impact categories.

	A1	A2	A3	Uncrushed	Products after 2 stages of crushing	Products after 3 stages of crushing	P4
Global warming potential total, GWP - total [kg CO2 eq.]	1.1	4.4e-1	5.2e-1	4.2e-1	4.7e-1	6.1e-1	0.0
Global warming potential fossil, GWP - fossil [kg CO2 eq.]	1.1	4.4e-1	4.2e-1	3.1e-1	3.7e-1	5.0e-1	0.0
Global warming potential biogenic, GWP - biogenic [kg CO2 eq.]	-3.0e-3	-4.3e-4	1.0e-1	1.0e-1	1.0e-1	1.0e-1	0.0
Global warming potential land use and land use change, GWP - LULUC [kg CO2 eq.]	3.1e-3	3.4e-3	8.2e-4	5.1e-4	6.9e-4	1.1e-3	0.0
Indicator for climate impact, GWP - GHG [kg CO2 eq.]	1.0	4.3e-1	5.1e-1	4.1e-1	4.6e-1	5.9e-1	0.0
Depletion potential of the stratospheric ozone layer, ODP [kg CFC-11 eq.]	4.1e-11	8.2e-17	8.8e-15	1.2e-15	5.6e-15	1.5e-14	0.0
Acidification potential, Accumulated Exceedance, AP [Mol H+ eq.]	9.7e-3	2.5e-3	1.3e-3	9.4e-4	1.2e-3	1.7e-3	0.0
Eutrophication potential, fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment, EP-freshwater [kg (PO4)3- eq.]	1.7e-6	1.3e-6	3.3e-6	6.8e-7	2.2e-6	5.6e-6	0.0
Eutrophication potential, fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment, EP - marine [kg N eq.]	3.6e-3	1.2e-3	4.4e-4	3.0e-4	3.8e-4	5.7e-4	0.0
Eutrophication potential, Accumulated Exceedance, EP-terrestrial [mol N eq.]	5.0e-2	1.3e-2	4.5e-3	3.3e-3	4.0e-3	5.5e-3	0.0
Formation potential of tropospheric ozone, POCP [kg NMVOC eq.]	8.1e-3	2.3e-3	1.1e-3	7.7e-4	9.5e-4	1.4e-3	0.0
Abiotic depletion potential for non-fossil resources, ADP- minerals & metals [kg Sb eq.]	6.7e-7	3.5e-8	1.6e-7	5.3e-8	1.1e-7	2.5e-7	0.0
Abiotic depletion potential for fossil resources, ADP-fossil fuels [MJ, net calorific value]	1.4e+1	0.1	1.8e+1	4.6	1.2e+1	2.9e+1	0.0
Water (user) deprivation potential, deprivation weighted water consumption, WDP [m3 world eq. deprived]	3.6e-1	7.0e-3	1.5e-1	1.0e-1	1.3e-1	2.0e-1	0.0

Figure 18. The core impact categories that are shown in the user interface.

The environmental impacts can be extracted with LCA and EPD reports in a Word format (also as a JSON, described in 4.8.5). These are generated at the bottom of the EPD and LCA Menu and are customized to the

information entered in the different tabs. The reports are in Word format to simplify the editing and enable additional information and illustrations to be added if needed for verifying the LCA and EPD documents.

See D5.4 for details about the content of the LCA and EPD reports and how they relate to the standard EN 15804.

4.8.3 Contribution Analysis

One of the critical analyses that is included in the reports is the contribution analysis. The different life cycle stages have different impacts on the total environmental burdens associated with the production of aggregates. These differences are given per product group to understand the significance of different life cycle stages on the overall environmental impact.

Similarly, different flows have different impacts on the total environmental burdens associated with the products. Specific resources will have the higher contribution compared to others in specific impact categories. The following five impact categories for different product groups are analysed:

- Global Warming Potential, GWP- total.
- Depletion potential of the stratospheric ozone layer, ODP.
- Acidification potential, Accumulated Exceedance, AP.
- Eutrophication potential, fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment, EP-freshwater; and
- Formation potential of tropospheric ozone, POCP.

Table 7 illustrates an example of a contribution analysis for a process that has three different product groups.

Table 7. Example of contribution analysis extracted from the LCA report

Product group	Impact category	Highest impact resource	% of total impact
Uncrushed	GWP-total	explosives	41.2
Uncrushed	ODP	explosives	100.0
Uncrushed	AP	explosives	62.2
Uncrushed	EP-freshwater (P)	diesel	59.9
Uncrushed	POCP	explosives	59.5
Products after 2 stages of crushing	GWP-total	explosives	40.0
Products after 2 stages of crushing	ODP	explosives	100.0
Products after 2 stages of crushing	AP	explosives	61.1
Products after 2 stages of crushing	EP-freshwater (P)	diesel	42.2
Products after 2 stages of crushing	POCP	explosives	58.6
Products after 3 stages of crushing	GWP-total	explosives	37.5
Products after 3 stages of crushing	ODP	explosives	100.0
Products after 3 stages of crushing	AP	explosives	58.8
Products after 3 stages of crushing	EP-freshwater (P)	energy	62.5
Products after 3 stages of crushing	POCP	explosives	56.6

4.8.4 Sensitivity Analysis

Various decisions need to be made throughout the quantification of the environmental impacts. These decisions and the inputs into the system will impact the result of the study. To evaluate how key data inputs and methodological choices could affect the results, a sensitivity analysis needs to be conducted where alternative scenarios have been modelled and compared to the final results.

This is not generated as the other results and the user needs to select inputs to vary and the increase or decrease in the input values. An example of this could be increasing the input of a lower-quality data set by 20% to see how much an assumption error in the input could affect the final results. An additional scenario would be to use a system input that has a high contribution, as identified from the contribution analysis and run the process model with a higher input of this consumable. Table 8 illustrates the sensitivity results table in the LCA report. The user defines at least one scenario for at least one product groups for the sensitivity analysis.

Table 8. The overview of the sensitivity analysis table.

Parameter describing environmental impacts	Baseline (total for A1-A3 per DU for Product Group [X])	Increase in significant input by X %	Change from baseline (%)
GWP-total			
GWP-fossil			
GWP-biogenic			
GWP-LULUC			
GWP-GHG			
ODP			
AP			
EP-freshwater			
EP-freshwater kg P			
EP-marine			
EP-terrestrial			
POCP			
ADP-minerals & metals			
ADP-fossil fuels			
WDP			

4.8.5 JSON

Due to the nature of LCA and EPD reporting, traceability is of great importance. Since this is the case, data fed into the platform, such as consumables, along with the LCA data used to assess the environmental impact must be contained in one file. This file can be the reports themselves, but when interacting with other systems such as the DataLake in DigiEcoQuarry, a dedicated file is the better choice. JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) is a convenient way to structure large amount of data, while also making it readable for verification by a human.

In Plantsmith, the JSON file is mirroring the LCA reports, meaning it is extensive enough to reproduce the calculations at a later date by a verifier. In DEQ, the JSON file is used to send the environmental impact of the pilot sites to the DataLake, from where some key information is sent to the PowerBI dashboards for the pilot sites to be viewed for improved monitoring.

4.8.6 Accessibility and interpretability: Competence development

Despite a large focus on usability during the development of Plantsmith, it is difficult for any user to jump straight into a new tool and use it directly to its full capabilities. Therefore, training material and courses are recommended for aggregate producers and individuals who are planning on using the platform for environmental assessment. These simulation routines can be used as a foundation for course development on platform use in the future to maximise the utility from such a tool.

5 Environmental Impacts in Quarries

The term "environment" is broad and can be applied in various contexts, ranging from our work or home settings to aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. As such, several delimitations have already been set and described in previous deliverables for the scope of the DEQ project (namely D1.4 and D5.4). These delimitations gave the project a clear starting point but still left some areas of doubt. Work to clarify further how to communicate, as well as understand further the extent to which different environmental impacts are addressed in the simulation tool, has been conducted in the project and are presented in section 5.1.

More importantly, as the project comes to an end, is considerations into how the knowledge gained through the project can be made available and aid the industry as a whole, not only individual quarries. One key mechanism for applying environmental knowledge to the industry is through standardization and certification. Section 5.2, therefore, focuses on future progression in already ongoing standardization processes in Europe, while also adding suggestions based on the findings in DEQ WP5.

5.1 Overall Impacts Assessment

One of the aims of implementing environmental assessment (LCA) connected to process simulations is to lead to reductions in environmental impact. It is important, however, to understand which environmental impacts are addressed using such tools, as environmental impact can be large and diverse effecting on local to global scales. To be able to define the limitations of such a broad topic, a comprehensive literature review was conducted on the possible environmental impacts of a quarry and published in Cleaner Environmental Systems (Lee et al., 2024). This review was used to identify which environmental aspects are addressed and which are excluded when applying the environmental assessment conducted through Plantsmith. An overview of this can be seen in Figure 19.

For the environmental aspects addressed, it is often stated that you cannot improve that which you do not measure. However, a key hypothesis for Task 5.4 is that the frequency of that measurement is also key to improve environmental performance. After the initial state zero assessment for the year 2019 presented in D5.4 to capture conditions prior to the commencement of the project, three of the pilot sites were assessed again for the production year of 2022. The results showed little to no improvement in environmental improvement, and in fact a worsening could be seen for some environmental aspects. The results indicate that infrequent measurement is not enough to achieve improvements in environmental performance, and promotes the use of more frequent assessment aspired to in the DEQ project.

For more details on the energy related environmental impacts, it is suggested to refer to the deliverable D5.3.

Figure 19: Environmental aspects, impacts and mechanisms not included in the Plantsmith environmental assessment (Lee, 2024).

5.2 Standardization and certification

Standardization and certification are common policy tools used to drive change across entire sectors. The focus within DEQ has been on standards within the EPD framework which are described in more detail in D5.4. However, the EPD framework is becoming increasingly leveraged within regulation in the EU as not only a tool to drive change, but as a compliance tool. For example, the environmental information within EPDs is seen as a way for companies to report some of their environmental concerns in the new CSRD regulations. Similarly, providing environmental data is now mandatory as part of the Construction Product Regulation (CPR) where EPDs align with what is required and are a way to meet this demand.

To match this continuously changing environment of regulation and certification, changes and updates are often coming in the EPD framework to meet the growing demands of what an EPD should provide, and to increase the trustworthiness of the information provided. Specific to aggregates regarding updates to the EPD framework, is the planned release of a sub-PCR for unbound aggregates. An overview of some changes and gaps where a sub-PCR can support aggregate producers are discussed in section 5.2.1.

As digitalization is one of the main aims of the DEQ project, how digitalization can be utilized for environmental assessment using standardization is then discussed in section 5.2.2.

5.2.1 Sub-PCR for Unbound Aggregates

The creation of a sub-PCR providing more guidance for aggregate producers beyond that given in EN 15804 is currently being led by the European Aggregates Association, UEPG. The generalizability of EN 15804 to match such a broad range of construction products can cause confusion for particular products in certain decisions for the background LCA. For aggregate producers, a particular challenge can be deciding where the system boundaries should be placed to create as much comparability between aggregate products as possible.

It can be particularly challenging for aggregate producers to set system boundaries when using recycled material as the main source of material into the production system. Production of recycled aggregates can consist of mineral waste materials originating from demolition works, discarded mineral construction products or rejected production of mineral construction products. Although the same declared units can be applied as for natural aggregates, there are several additional activities that can occur depending on the source material including the removal of contaminants, such as metals, plastics, wood, hazardous materials or other unwanted substances, before the material can be reintroduced into circulation. The EPD system focuses on the 'producer pays' principle which adds complexity to setting boundaries, as many sources can be from outside the aggregate product lifecycle, and so it can be difficult to ensure burdens are accounted for or, on the contrary, not double counted. Guidance on what activities should be included within the system boundaries for producers, and for which source materials can ease this process for producers and make communication clearer for interested stakeholders. Figure 20 provides some possible activities within the system boundaries for natural aggregates and recycled aggregates that could be useful if clarified in a sub-PCR.

Figure 20. Possible activities in the system boundaries that can be outlined in sub-PCR for natural aggregates. System boundaries for Recycled aggregates are given within the green box.

5.2.2 Digitalization for Environmental Assessment in the Industry

Implementing environmental assessment in the form of LCA is challenging for producers (Lee, et al., 2022), and digitalization is often discussed as an enabler for the implementation of environmental improvements (Chen, 2023). However, uptake is still low suggesting there are additional barriers in digitalization for environmental improvement in companies. Müller et al. (2018) identify three pillars for successful utilization of Industry 4.0, named as digitalization of processes, self-controlled production systems (also known as smart manufacturing), and inter-company connectivity.

Tackling inter-company connectivity has been a key objective for the IQS to allow compatibility across systems. Within the work of Task 5.4, interoperability between systems has been a key focus considering how inter-company connectivity is seen as integral for successful implementation of digital solutions. As part of this, an interview study was conducted and presented at the IMPC XXXI Congress investigating enablers and barriers to interoperability for environmental assessment (Lee, Asbjörnsson & Evertsson, 2024). The study identified 22 challenges and enablers across two distinct themes: human factors and technology. These have been used to suggest a roadmap towards achieving higher uptake of digital solutions that can be used for environmental assessment in quarries in the future that has been visualized in Figure 21.

The first step would be to inform aggregate producers, particularly those working in the quarries themselves, on the capabilities and practical applications of different digital technologies. Perceptions of digitalization were positive based on the results from the study, where the value that can be gained from digitalization is acknowledged. However, three challenges identified related to competence and expectations indicate that knowledge surrounding exactly what the benefits of digitalization for day-to-day operations is still low, and there is a misalignment in the expectations as to what digital technologies can enable. It is, therefore, suggested to use case study examples that are relatable for aggregate producers in informing and planning the use of digital technologies. Projects like DEQ can be helpful to showcase more concrete examples of where digital technologies can be used and benefit aggregate quarries.

Figure 21: Suggested three-step plan towards improved utilization of digital technologies for environmental assessment in the aggregates industry.

The second step suggested is to work towards a more harmonized system to ease implementation and avoid unnecessary delays for implementing multiple digital solutions that can work together. Standardization for the industry is one way in which this could be achieved, similar to that in the construction sector for BIM². However, by starting early in the digitalization process for the industry, multiple standards could be avoided leading to a much more concise, consistent, and less fragmented standardization ecosystem. This is suggested based on challenges identified across both themes related to language barriers, data management issues, the low level of digitalization perceived in the industry as well as standardization being lifted as an enabler. From the results of the study by Lee et al. (2022), a large emphasis would be on creating standardization for data format, important metadata, and nomenclature to improve machine readability of data, but also readability for humans involved in the processes.

Lastly, a need to invest in digital solutions from development through to implementation is seen. Economic investment has not emerged as a barrier, rather investment in knowledge and human capital has been identified in challenges related to lack of training, IT knowledge, and time shortages/ manpower for working with new digital solutions.

² For an introduction on BIM standardization see: A guide to understanding BIM standards: BIM Levels and Global BIM standards. Accessed via:

<https://www.advenser.com/2023/09/05/a-guide-to-understanding-bim-standards-bim-levels-and-global-bim-standards/>

6 System integration (developers guide)

Digitalization as an enabler for implementing environmental improvements requires significant development for a successful application. An integral part of the development of the process and environmental platform Plantsmith was the inclusion of the possibility of integrating the platform with 3rd party solutions, either as an embedded module or by establishing communication with external systems, enabling data exchange and interoperability. Key considerations have included standardizing data formats, ensuring connectivity, and maintaining compatibility with user workflows. By embedding the system into the larger platform, users gain enhanced functionality, centralized access, and a streamlined experience for managing complex processes, such as is the objective of the IQS

For details on the integration of Plantsmith in IQS, see D4.6: *Report in IQS, Services Integration and Deployment*, section 3.2.3.3, D4.2: *Report and IQS Design and Architecture*, section 4.1.2.3.9, and D5.4: *Report on Pre-verified EPD documentation for pilot plants based on historical data*.

6.1 Data Management

Effective data management is critical for digital platforms, especially when handling production data. It involves establishing robust data collection, storage, processing, and security systems to ensure accuracy and reliability. Within Plantsmith, the implementation of Django and PostgreSQL enables the backend data management. For user data managements, Excel templates have been created to guide data collection for Plantsmith, and good data management practices are encouraged³.

Django, paired with PostgreSQL, provides a robust framework for managing data in a web-based platform. Django's simplifies the interaction with PostgreSQL, allowing developers to define models in Python that translate directly into database tables, ensuring seamless data management. With PostgreSQL's support for advanced data types like JSON, the platform can efficiently store and query dynamic input data alongside structured model repository records. Django's built-in tools for migrations, security, and scalability make it easy to adapt the database schema and maintain data integrity as the platform evolves. Additionally, Django REST Framework enables the creation of APIs for efficient data exchange, while PostgreSQL ensures reliable performance and scalability for handling large datasets and complex queries. Together, Django and PostgreSQL form a scalable, secure, and developer-friendly foundation for managing production data on the platform.

Within DEQ, the data management is centralized in the CDMP, described in D4.4. See Figure 22 for the frontend application of the CDMP in DEQ.

³ For example, Data Management Best Practices from UC San Diego: <https://library.ucsd.edu/research-and-collections/research-data/plan-and-manage/data-management-best-practices.html>

Figure 22. The graphical user interface of the CDMP.

6.2 Communication protocols

Rest API is built in to the functionality in the Plantsmith platform. A REST API is a standardized approach to building and accessing web services, allowing systems to communicate over the internet using HTTP protocols. Actions are performed using standard HTTP methods such as GET, POST, PUT, and DELETE. REST APIs are flexible, scalable, and platform-independent. They commonly use data formats like JSON or XML for communication, enabling efficient and interoperable interactions across diverse systems. By adhering to a consistent and uniform structure, REST APIs simplify integration, enhance usability, and support the seamless exchange of data

Swagger is one of the tools available for Rest APIs and is used in integrating Plantsmith with the IQS. It provides a structured way to describe your API endpoints, their inputs, outputs, and functionalities, ensuring consistency and clarity. For example, using Swagger to retrieve Meta-data involves defining the relevant endpoints and their parameters in an XML or JSON format. Swagger then generates interactive API documentation, allowing developers to test endpoints directly in a user-friendly interface. See Figure 23 from D4.6.

Figure 23. List of the available endpoints from swagger for the implementation in IQS.

6.3 System trustworthiness

One challenge observed for implementing digital technologies for environmental assessment is validity: how can we trust the results that are produced? With complex systems where it becomes difficult to trace data directly to individual sources, it is an important topic to be addressed if large scale implementation is sought. Further research is recommended into how data collected through automated systems can be validated and ensure correct calibration/ readings from sensor technologies can be given to users in the future. One way that can help provide more transparency to digital systems such as the IQS to improve trustworthiness is providing concise and relevant documentation.

6.3.1 Documentation

Documentation is a key part of enabling trustworthiness in the system, particularly concerning the data used. Within Plantsmith, an example for documentation that can be provided concerning the LCA modules used within the platform is presented in Figure 24.

The new documentation template has been created for the LCA modules containing key information on the modules used for environmental calculations. This helps the user avoid any double counting, as well as verifiers in understanding the data and which databases have been used for background data. Further, it helps with maintenance of the system by providing a history of changes to datasets as updates are implemented. Further work is suggested with documentation for the platform to improve the trustworthiness and transparency of the models and calculations, in conjunction with the business plan to avoid publishing confidential information for the system as well.

Environmental Database Documentation

VERSION:

DATE:

AUTHORS:

This document includes metadata on LCA modules included in the EPD Berg environmental database used in the EPD add-on in Plantsmith.

Consumable Name

Summary Information	
<i>Consumable Name</i>	Name in Plantsmith
<i>Consumable reference no.</i>	Internal reference number to track updates to database and datasets within the database
<i>LCA module reference unit</i>	1 litre or 1 kg etc.
<i>In flow or out flow?</i>	Does it refer to a consumable, waste, or other flow in or out of the system
<i>LCA module implementation date</i>	Or validity period? Indication of when it was implemented into Plantsmith
<i>Dataset reference year</i>	Year for which the main dataset represents
<i>Database origin</i>	Database from which the main dataset originates
<i>Dataset description</i>	Main activities covered in the dataset (cradle to gate, cradle to construction site, cradle to end-of-use etc.)
<i>Main dataset reference</i>	Name of main dataset used in LCA module
<i>Geographical reference</i>	Which geographical area does the dataset represent?
<i>Characterization method used</i>	Name of characterization package used in creating the LCA module
<i>LCA standards applied?</i>	Any national or international standards that have been applied
<i>Transport to site included?</i>	AA equivalent from previous system
<i>Distance</i>	In reference to transport to site
<i>Load utilization</i>	In reference to transport to site
<i>Return trip included?</i>	In reference to transport to site
<i>Known emissions from correct use?</i>	Indicator as to whether use should be included
<i>Emissions from use included?</i>	If yes have they been included within the dataset or not?
<i>Included emissions</i>	Which emissions have been included
<i>Key assumptions not addressed above</i>	Other key information that should be noted when looking at the LCA module
<i>LCA module plan & software</i>	Illustration of the plan for the LCA module and the software used to develop the LCA module.

General Description:

A more detailed description of the LCA module and any rationale for assumptions/limitations in the module.

Results

Include the results for the reference unit in the characterization method used

Figure 24: Example of documentation that could be used to improve the transparency of the LCA modules included in Plantsmith for background data.

7 Conclusions

This report has outlined the development and application of simulation routines to apply environmental assessment in quarrying operations through the utilization of digital technologies, namely the online platform Plantsmith. Further, it discusses the integration of the Plantsmith platform into the IQS for a higher level of automation for data collection and KPI generation. The work conducted highlights the critical role of digitalization and advanced technologies in transforming the aggregates industry. By employing steady-state process modelling and modular LCA methodologies aligned with the EPD framework, the simulation routine enables more granular environmental profiling. This not only supports the creation of EPDs but also offers nearer real-time, actionable insights for producers aiming to enhance resource efficiency and reduce environmental burdens.

The integration of the Plantsmith platform within the IQS has proven effective in addressing challenges such as data variability, operational complexity, and the need for higher granularity in environmental assessments. By transitioning from traditional yearly reporting to more frequent and detailed data collection, quarry operators are more likely to identify inefficiencies and can, therefore, implement targeted improvements. Moreover, the platform's ability to automate data collection, facilitate modular analysis, and provide robust simulation capabilities establishes it as an exciting tool for advancing sustainability in quarrying operations.

The outcomes of this work underline the importance of adopting digital solutions and standardized assessment frameworks to meet increasing regulatory demands, such as those outlined in the CSRD. These tools not only help producers align with environmental regulations but also contribute to broader sustainability objectives, including reducing emissions, conserving natural resources, and enhancing operational transparency. Looking ahead, the methodologies and findings presented in this report provide a blueprint for broader industry adoption and future innovation. Recommendations for ongoing development include refining the Plantsmith platform, expanding its integration capabilities, and incorporating real-time calibration mechanisms to enhance accuracy further. As the industry continues to evolve, the insights gained from this project can inform policy updates and support the global transition toward a more sustainable aggregates sector.

8 References

The following references have been used for the preparation of this deliverable:

- D9.1: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan.
- D1.4 : Requirements for H&S improvement, Environmental impact minimisation and energy and resources efficiency report
- D5.4 : Pre-verified Environmental Product Declaration documentation for pilot plant based on historical data
- D5.3 : Overview of energy consumption of different quarrying process, connections and suggestions for reduction measures
- Pre-verified Environmental Product Declaration documentation for pilot plant based on historical data
- DIGIECOQUARRY Grant Agreement number 101003750.
- Chen, X. (2023). *Strengthening the Environmental Sustainability of Production Systems Through Digitalization*. [Doctoral thesis, Chalmers University of Technology.] ISBN: 978-91-7905-927-9
- Nascimento, D. L. M., Alencastro, V., Quelhas, O. L. G., Caiado, R. G. G., Garza-Reyes, J. A., Rocha-Lona, L., & Tortorella, G. (2019). Exploring Industry 4.0 technologies to enable circular economy practices in a manufacturing context. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 30(3), 607-627. DOI:10.1108/JMTM-03-2018-0071
- Ghobakhloo, M. (2020). Industry 4.0, digitization, and opportunities for sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 252, 119869. DOI:10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119869
- Lee, C., Papadopoulou, P., Asbjörnsson, G., Hulthén, E., & Evertsson, M. (2022). Understanding Current Challenges in Evaluating Environmental Impacts for Aggregate Producers through a Case Study in Western Sweden [Article]. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(3), Article 1200. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031200>
- Lee, C. (2024). *A Life Cycle Approach to Environmental Sustainability in Aggregate Production Systems. What Matters and For Whom?* (Publication no. IMS-2024-2) [Licentiate thesis, Chalmers University of Technology]. <https://research.chalmers.se/en/publication/540070>
- Lee, C., Sánchez, F., Asbjörnsson, G., & Evertsson, M. (2024, February). Application Of Production Simulation Combined With Site-Specific Data To Quantify The Environmental Performance Of Aggregate Products At Five Pilot Sites. In *Conference in Minerals Engineering*. Luleå, Sweden.
- Lee, C., Asbjörnsson, G., Hulthén, E., & Evertsson, M. (2024). The environmental impact of extraction: A holistic review of the quarry lifecycle. *Cleaner Environmental Systems*, 13, 100201. DOI:10.1016/j.cesys.2024.100201
- Lee, C., Asbjörnsson, G., & Evertsson, M. (2024, September). Down The Data Drain: How Can We Utilize Quarry Data For Environmental Assessment? In *XXXI IMPC - International Mineral Processing Congress*. Washington D.C., USA.
- Müller, J. M., Buliga, O., & Voigt, K.-I. (2018). Fortune favors the prepared: How SMEs approach business model innovations in Industry 4.0. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 132, 2-17. DOI:10.1016/j.techfore.2017.12.019

9 List of Figures

Figure 1. The system structure for Plantsmith	11
Figure 2. System structure of the IQS.	12
Figure 3: The input-process-output modular LCA method suggested for different manufacturing activities in a production chain by Brondi & Carpanzano (2011).....	13
Figure 4: An overview of the workflow highlighting user actions and components of the Plantsmith tool needed for conducting environmental assessment using the tool (Lee et al., 2024).	14
Figure 5: Illustration of the process followed during the assessment.....	16
Figure 6: An overview of common background and foreground data in an LCA study for construction products.	17
Figure 7: Different modules to which activities in the manufacturing process should be allocated for the production site in question. As can be seen, these activities are part of the whole lifecycle of the product. .	21
Figure 8. Empty canvas ready for flowsheet creation.....	23
Figure 9. A simple flowsheet of an aggregate process.....	23
Figure 10. A configuration of the stream properties in the source block.	24
Figure 11. Simulation log for a successfully completed simulation.....	31
Figure 12. Results button within the Plantsmith interface.....	32
Figure 13. Report generation buttons within the Plantsmith interface.	32
Figure 14. Particle size distribution for all the streams.	32
Figure 15. Specific energy for all the streams.	33
Figure 16. Example of results for the stream and unit model.....	33
Figure 17: EPD and LCA Menu in the platform.....	34
Figure 18. The core impact categories that are shown in the user interface.....	34
Figure 19: Environmental aspects, impacts and mechanisms not included in the Plantsmith environmental assessment (Lee, 2024).....	39
Figure 20. System Boundaries according to c-PCR for natural aggregates. System boundaries for Recycled aggregates are within the green box	41
Figure 21: Suggested three-step plan towards improved utilization of digital technologies for environmental assessment in the aggregates industry.	42
Figure 22. The graphical user interface of the CDMP.	44
Figure 23. List of the available endpoints from swagger for the implementation in IQS.....	45
Figure 25: Example of documentation that could be used to improve the transparency of the LCA modules included in Plantsmith for background data.	47

10 List of Tables

Table 1: Production data from an annual production.....	18
Table 2: Product level data	18
Table 3: Consumable data from the reference year	19
Table 4: Waste data	19
Table 5: Product level data	26
Table 6: Description of the use of yellow machines.....	27
Table 7. Example of contribution analysis extracted from the LCA report	36
Table 8. The overview of the sensitivity analysis table.....	37

Annex I. Data Collection Guide

From EPD berg 2

All data collected must represent the reference year for the study. This means any production figures, purchase information, technical set-up should be representative of that year. Any missing datasets or data collected from another production year must be clearly stated. Site specific data will need to be collected for the following categories:

- **Technical data** referring to the set-up of machinery and mass flows through the specific plant. This data is needed to build the initial model.
- **Production data** for all products and material inputs from the reference year.
- **Consumption data** including system inputs and waste outputs. System inputs consisting of data on how much energy, water, explosives, and various materials have gone into the production process. Waste Outputs where data on which products and how much of each product was produced along with any waste produced in the process. Data concerning production fractions can be imported from the simulator and compared against any recorded production data.

Site-Specific Data Descriptions

<i>Technical Data</i>	
Data Required	Data description
Mass flow for feeder stockpiles	This figure should represent the year of production or a typical day in the reference year. The data should be given in tonnes per hour (tph)
Production hours	This should give the total number of hours within the reference year where production took place.
Machine settings	This includes the average CSS used and the Eccentric Throw for crushers, and the Power Draw and Aperture for screeners
Material description	This includes the Bulk density, Work Index, and Moisture content if known.
<i>Production Data</i>	
Data Required	Data description
Total Yearly Production	The total stock produced during the reference year.
Individual Product Production Values	The total of each individual product produced in the reference year.
Total blasted material	The total amount of material blasted in the reference year
Total Entrepreneur Material	The total amount of material brought to the site from secondary sources (e.g. tunnel blasting).

<i>Consumption Data</i>	
Data Required	Data description
Diesel Consumption	Diesel consumption for all machines from crushing equipment to yellow machines and drilling. This can be collected, for example, from sensor data on machines or from invoices for the purchased amount of diesel. PLEASE NOTE: some of this data may need to be collected from sub-contractors.
Electricity Consumption	Electricity used for all on-site activities, from office use and on-site lighting to machine use. This can be collected, for example, from sensor data or from invoices.
Water Consumption	Water use for all activities including, but not limited to, dust minimisation, product washing, and general site consumption.
Explosives	The total amount of explosives used in every blast for the reference year. This can be taken, for example, from blast project reports or invoices.
Oil	This refers to all lubricants and hydraulic oil used during the year to maintain the machinery on-site. This can be taken, for example, from invoices or storage records.
Metals	This refers to any metal parts required for replacement or operation e.g. screen panels. This can be taken, for example, from invoices or product specifications.
Rubber	This refers to all tyres or rubber belts that are replaced on any transports during the reference year. Weights for tyres can be found on the product specifications. For reference a 26.5 R25 tyre for the Volvo L150H weighs approx. 500kg.
Chemicals	This refers to antifreeze and chemical additions to fuels/ yellow machines that are not lubricants, for example AdBlue or similar.
Salt	This refers to any salt products that are needed for site maintenance or that are mixed with end products.
Plastics	This refers to plastic products used in the production process, for example, screening panels. If data on the plastic content of any coated products can also be acquired, this can be included here.

<i>Consumption Data (Waste)</i>	
Data Required	Data description
Municipal solid waste	This category refers to general non-hazardous waste from the site. This is modelled on the assumption the waste will be incinerated.
Hazardous Waste	Refers to any waste from the site that is classed as hazardous e.g. batteries, chemicals etc.
Waste for Recycling	Refers to any waste that is recycled from site.